

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Upland rice varieties released in Brazil

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The National Research Center for Rice and Beans (EMBRAPA/CNPAF) started the work on rice in 1976. The first 2 yr were dedicated to national and international germplasm collection and studies on available genetic variability. In 1978, the first crosses were made at CNPAF, and evaluation started. In 1983, a national evaluation network was organized.

Varieties released in 1985 are Arroz BR 4 (IAC 5544/Dourado Precoce), EMCAPA 01 (IAC 5544/ Dourado Precoce), Cuiabana (IAC 47/SR 2041-50-1), Rio Paranaíba (IAC 47/63-83), Araguaia (IAC 47/TOS 2578/7-4-2-3-

Potential area (ha) to be covered by the upland rice cultivars released in Brazil since 1985.

B2), Guarani (IAC 25/63-83) and Centro America (IAC 25/63-83). These cultivars outyield local checks and are blast resistant.

The figure shows the potential area to be covered by the new releases, representing about 70% of the total upland rice area of Brazil. □

Two medium to early-maturing rice varieties for northwest India

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IARI recently released 2 early-maturing varieties (120-125 d), Pusa 169 and Pusa 205, for general cultivation.

Pusa 169, derived from a cross of IR28 with Pusa 140-56, and Pusa 205, derived from a cross of IR28 with Pusa

Table 1. Relative yield performance of Pusa 169 (IET7278) in All India Coordinated Yield Trials (AICRIP) (UVT-2).

Season, year	Yield (t/ha)		
	Pusa 169	Rasi	Ratna
Kharif 1980	4.6	3.7	4.1
Kharif 1981	4.3	3.7	4.2
Kharif 1982	4.8	3.8	4.4

Table 2. Relative yield performance of Pusa 205 (IET7279) in All India Coordinated Yield Trials (UVT-2).

Season, year	Yield (t/ha)		
	Pusa 205	IR36	Rasi
Kharif 1983	4.0	3.6	3.5
Rabi 1984	5.5	5.1	4.9
Kharif 1984	3.6	2.8	3.0
Rabi 1985	4.3	3.6	3.6

33-18, were identified as superior in yield performance in the medium-early and early groups in All India Coordinated Yield Trials and various on-farm and minikit trials (Table 1, 2). Yields almost equal those of popular medium-duration varieties, although the 2 varieties mature 2 wk earlier. Both varieties are moderately resistant to bacterial blight, and Pusa 205 is resistant to blast. Both have long slender grains and good cooking quality. Pusa 169 was released

in 1986 for Haryana, Punjab, western Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal, and Karnataka; Pusa 205 for Punjab, West Bengal, and Orissa. □

Performance of improved rice varieties in farmers' fields in Bhutan

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Five improved rice varieties (one tall, four semidwarf) were evaluated at seven typical farmers' fields in the Wangdiphodrang-Punakha valley in 1986. The sites were at altitudes between 1,250 m and 1,500 m. Soils were loam to sandy loam and sandy clay loam with pH 5.6-6.9 and 0.9-1.7% organic C.

Gain yield of improved rice varieties at 7 farmers' fields in Wangdiphodrang-Punakha, Bhutan, 1986.

Item	Changoytang Punakha	Richa Punakha	Zomleytang Punakha	Khurutang Punakha	Misina Wangdiphodrang	Bajo Wangdiphodrang	Techuzamba Wangdiphodrang	Mean
<i>Soil characteristics</i>								
pH	6.8	5.6	6.9	5.9	5.7	6.4	5.9	
Organic C (%)	1.40	1.01	0.86	1.10	0.89	1.43	1.66	
Olsen P (ppm)	21	2.5	2.1	6.6	nil	16	13	
FYM (t/ha)	12	14	6	20	10	12	(applied to preceding wheat)	
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>								
IR36	5.6	6.0	4.5	5.1	3.5	3.4	7.0	5.0
IR64	5.5	6.7	4.5	5.0	3.8	3.6	7.6	5.2
Milyang 49	4.2	5.7	4.2	4.1	3.1	3.0	6.2	4.4
IR25670-15-2-3	3.5	5.2	3.8	3.7	3.2	3.2	5.7	4.1
Local check	4.5	6.3	4.0	3.3	3.4	3.1	6.8	4.5
Site mean	4.6	6.0	4.2	4.2	3.4	3.2	3.3	
CV (%)	7.0	6.2	3.9	8.9	8.6	5.6	4.2	
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.7	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.3	0.5	

Olsen available P ranged from 2.1 to 21 ppm (see table). Levels of available K and other plant nutrients were generally adequate. The land was manured and prepared by cooperator farmers. Estimates of farmyard manure (FYM) applied at each site are shown in the table.

Seedlings of test varieties IR36, IR64, Milyang 49, IR25670-15-2-3, and K39-96-1-1-1-2, and the local check varieties were raised in farmers' dry bed nurseries and (except the check varieties) in standby nurseries at CARD in Apr and early May. In June, seedlings of each variety from farmers' nurseries (or from CARD) were transplanted in line at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm in 2 × 5 m plots at each site. The plots were arranged in a randomized complete block with three replications per site. Weedings were by rotary weeder and by hand once or twice between 22 and 43 d after transplanting, depending on weed pressure. Irrigations were managed by cooperator farmers. K39-96-1-1-1-2 matured considerably earlier than the other varieties, but no representative yields were obtained because it was seriously damaged by rats at most sites. There were no other significant pests or diseases. Plot yields of the remaining varieties were computed at 14% moisture content.

IR36 and IR64 were consistently good, and Milyang 49 and IR25670-15-2-3 consistently poor across sites. Individual check variety yields fluctuated substantially across sites,

resulting in a significant (P=0.05) site × variety interaction in a combined analysis of variance of all sites. Using the site × variety mean square for trend examination across sites showed IR36 and IR64 to be highly significantly superior (P=0.01) to Milyang 49 and IR25670-15-2-3. The latter two did not significantly differ from the check varieties at all sites: IR64 yield was consistently higher than that of the check varieties (significant at five sites) and tended to be higher than that of

IR36, although this difference was not significant in the combined site analysis of variance. IR64 is taller than IR36, has stiffer straw and, because of its intermediate amylose grain, is similar in eating quality, to local varieties. Like IR36, however, it is susceptible to drought stress in local dry bed nurseries and to cold stress if planted toward the end of the local planting season.

IR64 showed wide adaptability and may be more suitable than IR36 for increasing rice output in the valley. □

IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, a new, medium-duration rice variety released in Tamil Nadu as ADT38

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IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, isolated from the cross IR1529-680-3-2/IR4432-52-6-4// IR7963-30-2 and locally designated AD85004, was identified as the most promising high-yielding entry under thaladi (Oct-Jan) situations in the Cauvery Delta zone. This cultivar was evaluated at TNRRI for 4 yr. Based on its consistent performance, it was released in May 1987 as ADT38 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu in samba and thaladi seasons, as an alternate to IR20 and Co 43.

The mean grain yield over 4 yr in research station trials (5.9 t/ha) showed

Table 1. Performance of ADT38 in research station and adaptive research trials. Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1983-86.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	ADT38	Co 43	IR20
<i>Research station trials</i>			
1983	7.2	5.7	4.2
1984	5.3	4.4	4.3
1985	6.0	5.1	4.9
1986	5.0	4.2	3.5
Mean	5.9	4.9	4.3
<i>Adaptive research trials^a</i>			
1986	6.2	5.2	5.5

^a37 locations.

20 and 37% increases over Co 43 and IR20 (Table 1). In adaptive research trials in 37 farmers' fields, mean grain yield (6.2 t/ha) showed 19 and 13% increases over Co 43 and IR20. Its overall performance in the trials of All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project and the International Rice